

Interior design and furniture in traditional dwellings in the old towns between modernity and preservation of cultural heritage (a special case in the old city of hebron)

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Abstract

This paper discusses the repercussions, challenges, and conditions imposed by the living occupancy in traditional dwellings with the signature spatial organization in the old cities in general and in the Old City of Hebron/Palestine in particular. moreover, this paper examines the interior design of these dwellings in terms of wooden furniture fixed or movable, facilities such as bathrooms and kitchens, the distribution of furniture and its shape, and design, furthermore, illustrate the problem that is caused by living in traditional dwellings built in ancient time, containing patterns of spatial designs that were of use in the past but no longer suit the current needs of the inhabitants and modernity. many building foundations in this paper go back to the Mamluk period, However, the rest of them goes back to the Ottoman period. This paper aims to study the possibility of adapting the characteristics and components of traditional dwellings and formulate new models and solutions that enable the inhabitants of these dwellings to live in them while providing comfort and well-being without having to resort to the destruction and total removal of the internal components or replacing them with the modern style, which may not suit the aesthetics and structural feature. in addition, maintain its heritage value, by applying several measures that ensure the best results, within an objective analytical methodology including identifying a few selected models of traditional dwellings, conducting a study, and inheriting it, to reach results advancing the preservation of the cultural heritage and achieving sustainability.

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Keywords

Interior components of the dwelling; wooden furniture; traditional dwelling; Hebron Old City; heritage value.

1. Introduction

The subject of residential buildings relates to the daily details of housing including the special needs of the inhabitants. each dwelling has a classification upon some factors such as social, economic, and religious, these factors form a special bond that completes each other. These factors are shown in the walls, floors, and ceilings with many purposes that meet the needs of the family that inhabits the dwelling, which is a part of the adaptataion process to modern life routines and habits. The interior decoration of traditional residences receives a great deal of attention which are the subject of this research, with the tendency to rehabilitate historical buildings, residential dwellings in particular, instates the need to repurpose the internal and functional components, and in order to find new functions that are as similar to the original function as possible, we need to find common and close factors for modern living patterns that take into account an acceptable adaptation, and ensure the continuation of the maintenance process and periodic preservation of residential buildings, (Ahmad . Hatem .1 January 2022. p 267). The process of readjustment, maintenance, and restoration must take into account the nature of the surrounding neighborhood and its inhabitants to create its own spatial identity, in which they can live within the cultural, social, and religion life they recognize, so

it is an important factor for the success of any restoration process and reusing the space. There is no doubt that the study of successful models around the world is an important factor to study the methods of restoration and reuse in a way that suits modernity and contemporary design, some of these successful cases experiences are as in the next examples below.

The first case is an Italian country house, dating back to the seventeenth century, which was used in the past as a mill. The dwelling maintained distinctive architectural elements including arches and the use of stones in construction, it has been abandoned for thirty years before designer Palomba Serafini did a specialized study on the interior design of the building. followed by a restoration of the dwelling to a more modern space to suit the current use and the era's requirements while preserving the original essence of the building. This was done in the following steps: First cleaning the stone walls and then painting them white, the stone floors were remodeled, the skylights were opened to bring natural lighting into the interior, and the furniture chosen was characterized by simplicity and modernity in earthy colors, using simple carpets that fit the traditional dwelling, finally the accessories that added vitality to the place such as side lighting and the use of natural wood, (est magazine issue 27. Rayner, Melia.2017) Figure 1.

Figure 1 An Italian Country House design by Palomba Serafini Photographed by Francisco Polisio est magazine issue 27.2017.

In the second case, the Interior design might follow the philosophy of the designer as in this example from Japan, in this example, a dwelling built in the fifteenth century in the ancient village of Ushisar, a site of an ancient monastery, characterized by the construction of arches and stone walls, the interior design of this building has tended to restore simplicity and originality within a philosophical concept called wabi-sabi. Which is inspired by nature, its materials differ from luxury, by heading towards rural elegance using simple materials that serve the place, with some accessories such as pottery and vases (Rizzoli. 2018) Figure 2.

Figure 2 wabi-sabi Japanese house. Rizzoli. (2018) <https://assets.hiphotels.com>

Elsewhere in Lebanon where the third example is located in the area of Msaytbeh, a house Once known as the Tower of Musaytbeh Named after the land where it stands figure 3. The history of this family house dates back to 1845 when the ground floor was built. As was customary in important houses at the time, it also included stables for the horses. A new floor was added in 1871, and restoration work started in 2017 by the architect and interior designer Rabih Geha, in the interior design of this restored dwelling that was inhabited by a family, we can notice the richness in details, interior furniture, and the treatment of interior walls, accessories, and antiques, with attention to lighting and air conditioning keeping up with a contemporary design in some important aspects whether in the interior design or the mechanics of the dwelling's electrical and sanitary extensions, to create a house that suites the inhabitants, moreover respect the building's originality and heritage status. Many models may study the integration of the historical building and contemporary design through restoration and treatment, followed by the study of suitable furniture (Sarup. April 11, 2022).

Figure 3. 200-Year-Old Beirut Mansion(April 11, 2022) . by Pratyush Sarup. Photography Cherine Jokhdar

1.1. Problem statement

Old towns in general and the old town of Hebron, in particular, are characterized by the diversity of historical periods, which extends for over 400 years. This cultural diversity arises some difficulties that affect the lifestyle of the inhabitants, which needs to be studied to come up with the proper solution that preserves the cultural and aesthetic identity of these dwellings without losing their authentic heritage. This paper aims to answer the following questions:

- Are there problems and needs facing the inhabitants of traditional dwellings in terms of the interior design of their own homes?
- What are the most important steps that must be followed to preserve the aesthetic components in the design of fixed and mobile interior furniture in traditional dwellings in which the people still inhabitant?

1.2. Methodology

This paper follows the descriptive and analytical scientific method through various means of interviewing, observation, and using various photography tools, computer drawings, documentation, drawing architectural plans, and detailed drawings and studies by scanning and documenting the houses used as examples in this paper.

2. Comparative analysis of case studies

This section of the research presents a qualitative analysis of some case studies. These cases are selected according to a number of principles that encompass conservation, and heritage building. A study was made on four models of the Old City of Hebron. These dwelling plans will be explained and clarified with the following pictures, the factors and selection criteria that the case studies are based on include:

- The selected dwellings contain distinct aesthetic elements of Islamic architecture.
- All the previous dwellings are located within the old town and their origins go back to the Ottoman period with Mamluk origins extended to the British Mandate era.
- all the housing units in which the study was conducted, had no previous studies or plans made, therefore, this study is considered original research that benefits researchers and the inhabitants of the old town.
- The selected dwellings are divided into two parts: a part that the owners have lived in since ancient times, and a part of the inhabitants who rent these dwellings.
- The dwellings that have been studied have been restored by the Hebron Reconstruction Committee and still require further maintenance and rehabilitation.
- The old town of Hebron is characterized by the diversity of the components of aesthetics and interior design, which gives distinction to it, and the most important feature is the diversity of fixed and mobile furniture.

Note. A special key icon was used to number the spaces and zoning of the dwelling to make it easy to follow the description and Cabinet and Niche coding by location and use as follows:

G. for the ground floor, F . for the first floor, R. for rooms, A,B, C, . front elevation

2.1 Case 1: Al-Rajbi family residence

The residential dwelling consists of a group of superimposed floors that were formed during different stages of the dwelling’s life, which is likely to date back to the beginning of the nineteenth century or before. Arches and two types of domes were used, including the fan-shaped dome known in the Mamluk and Ottoman periods. design is shown in figure 4. Let's start with the bedrooms, room 1. consists of the bed, cabinets, and their accessories, we note the presence of curves and arches that do not fit the furniture in the room as a traditional dwelling, and the quality of modern wood such as Formica used in the bedroom did not fit the traditional dwelling in terms of interior design table 1, the salon in room 1, located on a three-step platform and consists of a number of wall cabinets, most of them without shutters, as well as a mattress closet (mutawa) and allwejaq, the living room indicates a change in the use of the room, which was most likely the living room of the family in the past, and room 2 is used as a kitchen. We note the presence of the arched wall and untreated curves with furniture that suits it in terms of shape and purpose and in contrast with the design of the kitchen Which leads to deformation in its shape, a recommendation to make a suitable design for storage. Table 1.

Figure 4 .plan and section of Al-Rajbi family residence detailing rooms source author 2022

Table 1 current use of the room and Cabinets and Niche in Al-Rajbi dwelling place source author 2022

Cabinet and Niche coding by location and use	The current use of the room and Cabinet	The problem	image	plan
GR1A Wall Niche GR1B mattress closet (Almatawa) GR1C Wall Cabinets GR1D Wall Cabinets GR1E wejaq	Currently used as a salon guest room	All wall cabinets were taken off and left untreated, while another niche was left without use, and the wejaq was turned into a storage area.		

<p>GR2IA Wall Cabinet GR1B Wall Cabinet</p>	<p>Currently used as a kitchen for the family and the openings were used as a sink with cabinets placed in front of the open arches</p>	<p>The inconsistency of the used furniture, wall cabinets, and the original vaults shapes in the room, led to the loss of the aesthetic value of historece room</p>		
<p>F1R3A Wall Cabinet</p>	<p>Currently used as a bedroom with the bed placed in front of the closet opening</p>	<p>The bed in the bedroom does not fit the design of the arched wall behind the head of the bed, as well as the fixed side of the Dresser next to the bed-covered Vaults,</p>		

2.2 Case 2: Salhab family residence

The dwelling was built over several periods dating back to the middle of the nineteenth century. The entrance, which is a semi-broken main stone staircase, leads through a semi-roofed arch, and through the stone entrance, which leads to the main covered courtyard, which can be accessed directly from the entrance. The construction method of the dwelling is based on traditional construction, which is the vaulted fan arch system. it starts with, room 2, the bedrooms consist of separate beds, wardrobes, and accessories, there aren't many details about the bedrooms. Room 1, The living room (Al-Liwan), located in front of the main entrance and next to the kitchen, where the vaulted ceiling and you can not that the furniture pieces in this room are mineless. Then salon room 3, where the wooden wall cabinet (Al Namliya, which is used to store the requirements and needs of the household utensils, with painted light wood, and glass on the upper shelves of the cabinet, and drawers in the lower area Table 2, Then the kitchen, which has been built in the balcony, the lack of cupboards results from with the small space of the kitchen, which needs more studies to design a solution to set up sanitary fittings, As for the newly added bathroom, it needs extensions to suit its purpose, Table 2.

Figure 4 plan and section of residence of the Salhab family residence source author 2022

Table 2 current use of the room and Niches in All Salhab's dwelling source author 2022

Cabinet and Niche coding by location and use	The current use of the room	The problem	image	plan
GR1 No cabinets	Currently used as a living space for the family Liwan and the balcony is used as a space for the kitchen	The lack of proper design of furnitthat suits the shape of arches in the room and kitchen creates a special design of wall cabinets and niches, including their unsuitability for modern use.		
GR2 No wall cabinet	Currently used as a space for sleeping	The room does not contain furniture and does need redesigning to cope with the need of the inhabitant		
GR3A wall cabinet (namlia) GR3B Wall Niche	Currently used as a saloon room	The inconsistency of the shape of the cabinets with the interior space of the room led to the loss of the aesthetic value of the shape of theNiche.		

2.3 Case 3: The Qufaishah residence

The dwelling consists of three levels: ground level (built at the end of the nineteenth century -Ottoman era- first level -built at the beginning of the twentieth century- second level -built at the beginning of the twentieth century-, the design of the Qafisha's dwelling has a beautiful design with a variety of architectural model's and Details, this diversity is due to a number of reasons, one of them is that the dwelling was built in stages in which the construction methods and models varied, second the richness of its first owner that reflected on its way of construction. The traditional construction method depends on the presence of the arch system as approved in the roofing using corner bends and dispensing with the fan-domes system, which is a different stage from the first stages For the construction Figure 5 for the Interior design we start with the bedrooms, rooms 1, 2, 3, and 4, where we notice several spaces that were used as bedrooms, due to the presence of two families living in them. notice the arches in the walls and ceilings, and the replacement of cupboards and accessories in the room, one of the most important problems that appear in most rooms is the presence of a number of arches in several rooms. the Arches and domes Wall Cabinets with a depth of 37 cm. As a result of the lack of attention to maintenance, damages appeared including the loss of some of its shutters, as well as the instability of its drawers, paint damage, and rotting of the wall behind it, which is not currently in use, besides its inconsistency with its size and shape table .3 .Which needs to be re-designed to suit it, then the kitchen and its accessories from spaces for cooking, storage, and refrigeration, the problem of repurposing the room to become a kitchen, as it wasn't studied by a designer, the kitchen accessories and equipment are crowded because they do not find a suitable space in the design, also the need to add new tiles to some walls behind the sink to meet the modern needs, table 3. As for the bathroom, it was added to the residential building using a new system of construction and materials.

Figure 5 plan of Qafisha family residence encoding of the rooms and Niche, source author 2022

Table 3 current use of the room and Niches in Qafisha family dwelling source author 2022

Cabinet and Niche coding by location and use	The current use of the room	The problem	image	plan
F1R1A mattress Niche (Almatawa) F1R1B Wall Cabinet	Currently used as a salon guest room with 2 wall niches	All wall cabinets were taken off and left untreated, and some furniture covered the Almatawa Niche changing its original use, so it needs to Reuse cabinets and Niches to suit the residents' special needs		
F1R2IA Wall Cabinets	Currently used as a kitchen for the family and the openings were used as a sink with cabinets placed in front of the open arches	The loss of the beauty of the arches in the cabinets and their inconsistency led to the loss of their aesthetic value Create a special design of wall cabinets and niches, including their unsuitability for modern use.		
F1R3A Wall Cabinet	Currently used as a bedroom for boys	The contradiction of furniture in the interior design of the room, which is based on the design of arches in the walls, as well as in the design of the bed, which comes in the form of a cover on the original arch.		
F1R4A mattress closet (Almatawa) F1R4B Wall Niche	Currently used as a multi-purpose room and children's sleeping room	The traditional (Wall Niche) design, suffers from drawers damage and needs a redesign for better reuse, and the cabinet does not cop with the style furniture of the room. so it needs to Reuse cabinets and Niches to suit the residents' special needs		

<p>F1R5 No wall niches and have arches</p>	<p>Currently used as a master bedroom</p>	<p>The bedroom does not fit the arches in the room.</p>		
<p>F1K1IA Wall Cabinet F1KB Wall Niche</p>	<p>Currently used as a kitchen</p>	<p>The use of wall cabinets as a niche for supplies doesn't cope with the current design and space, and the walls need s tilling and more cabinets and space for Creating a special design of wall cabinets and niches, including their unsuitability for modern use.</p>		
<p>F1KI2 No wall cabinets</p>	<p>Currently used as a kitchen</p>	<p>There is difficulty in using the kitchen because of the lack of cabinets and the presence of arches in the ceiling with side knees. It needs to Create a special design of wall cabinets and niches, including their unsuitability for modern use</p>		

2.4 Case 4: Fawzi Al-Rajbi's residence

The dwelling expresses the Arab-Islamic architecture at the beginning of the Ottoman era and continued for a number of periods. The exact date of the original construction is not known, but from a study of the history of the neighborhood, we find that the origins of its construction are the Mamluk era, and the historical eras followed it with a number of modifications for each era, which expresses the aesthetics of Islamic architecture. The access to the Al-Rajbi family dwelling is from one of the courtyards of the neighborhood of Bani Dar, connected through an arch with a half-barrel arch that leads to a rectangular courtyard, by observing the sectors in Fawzy's residence, we find a number of arches in some of the rooms with the disappearance of the wooden wall cabinets Figure 6, the distribution of rooms and the interior design comes in succession. It was inconsistent with the room as in Table 4, then the living rooms. As there is not much furniture in it, and it was suitable with the old dwelling, Table. 4, then the kitchen area, as the room was converted into a kitchen, which was originally designed as a bedroom, that includes spaces for cooking, storage, and refrigeration, where we notice poor organization in a way that does not fit the requirements of the dwelling's Modern housing, that originates the need to re-design it to suit the measurements and the situation of the old dwelling.

Figure 6 plans and section of Fawzi Al-Rajbi's residence source author 2022

Table . 4 current use of the room and Niches in Fawzi Al, Rajabi Residence source author 2022

Cabinet and Niche coding by location and use	The current use of the room	The problem	image	plan
GR1AWall Cabinets G R1B wall niches mattress closet (Almatawa)	Current use as a salon guest room with 2 wall niches	All wall cabinets were taken off and left untreated. so it needs to Reuse cabinets and Niches to suit the residents' special needs		
G R 2 A wall niches (Almatawa) mattress closet G R 2 B Wall Niche GR2C allwejaq GR2DWall Nich	Current use as a multi-purpose room.	All wooden shelves were taken off and a curtain was used in A, B Adapting and maintaining the current design of the cabinets and Niche without changing their original design.		
GR3A Wall Niche GR3B allwejaq	Current use as a kitchen.	Create a special design of wall cabinets and niches, including their unsuitability for modern use. of the stove, refrigerator, and the rest of the kitchen accessories or tools.		
FIR1A Wall Niche FIR1B wall niches (Almatawa) mattress closet FIR1C wall niches	Current use as a master bedroom	Arches in the interior facades and their conflict with the bed and wall niches and their conflict with the niches of the bedrooms and (Almatawa)		

3. Analysis of case studies

This part of the study deals with a statistical study of several dwellings in the Old City of Hebron, within an analytical study, a questionnaire, to study and understand the situation of furniture and the interior design in the traditional dwellings, and the way the resident of their houses react and deal with their own homes, the number of this sample is 19. The following statistical methods were used to verify the study's objectives and verify its hypotheses. Frequent distribution of answers and percentages, graphs; all of which were collected by the authors of the paper. The study samples were selected based on several criteria, including:

1- Place of residence: where a study was conducted on 10 different areas in the old city of Hebron, Table. 5.

Table 5 frequency distribution of study subjects conducted in 10 different areas in the old city of Hebron source author 2022

Place of residence	Number	Percentage
Al, Shallala Street	3	15.8%
Al-Qazzazin Lane	5	26.3%
Bani Dar Quarter	2	10.5%
Qaitoun Lane	1	5.3%
Al-Mashareqah Lane	2	10.5%
Al-Aqaba Lane	1	5.3%
Al, Dabouya	2	10.5%
The mouse pierced	1	5.3%
Milk Market	1	5.3%
Khalat Hadour	1	5.3%
Total	19	100%

2- Age of the dwelling:

Figure 6 Frequency distribution of study subjects according to the age of the dwelling source author 2022

3- Number of rooms:

Table 6 frequency distribution of study subjects by the number of rooms source author 2022

Number of rooms	Number	Percentage
1 – 3 Rooms	6	31.6%
4 – 7 rooms	5	26.3%
8 rooms and above	8	42.1%
Total	19	100%

4- Number of niches in the housing:

Table 7 Frequency distribution of study personnel according to the number of niches source author 2022

Number of cabinets and Niches	Number	Percentage
1 – 3 cabinets and Niche	10	52.6%
4 – 7 cabinets and Niche	2	10.5%
8 cabinets above	7	36.8%
Total	19	100%

5- Kitchen mode:

Table 8 studies subjects' frequency distribution according to the kitchen situation source author 2022

Kitchen mode	Number	Percentage
Traditional cabinets and Niche	10	52.6%
Modern cabinets and Niche	9	47.4%
Total	19	100%

It is clear from table 8 that the situation of kitchen cabinets and niches for most of the study members is (traditional cabinets) where they reached 10 individuals and constitute (52.6%), while the number of those who put the place for kitchen cabinets upon self-choice (modern cabinets) was 9 individuals constituting (47.4%).

4. Survey Results

As a part of this paper, a survey of inhabitants was distributed, focusing on the following questions:

Do you use wall niches regularly?

Do you find obstacles when buying furniture in your traditional home?

Do you suffer from constant moisture in the walls of old cupboards?

Do you keep the current design of the cabinets and Niche unchanged?

Do you reuse cabinets and Niche to suit your own needs?

Do you re-repair the damaged cabinets and Niche as soon as any damage occurs to them?

• **The first statement came Do you use wall niches regularly?** Frequency distribution of the answers for the study sample members to the first statement It is clear from Figure 7 that the answer for the majority of the study members is (agree), as their number reached (9) individuals and constituted (47.4%), followed by those whose answer is (agree). Strongly) with (5) individuals at a rate of (26.3%), while the number of those who answered (neutral) was (4) individuals at a rate of (21.1%).

Figure 7 first statement. source author 2022

• **The second statement came: Do you find obstacles when buying furniture in your traditional home?** Frequent distribution of the answers of the study sample members to the It is clear in Figure 18 that the answer for the majority of the study members is (I agree), as their number reached (11) individuals and constituted (57.9). %), followed by those who answered (strongly agree) with (6) individuals at a rate of (31.6%), while the number of those who answered (neutral) reached two individuals at a rate of (10.5%).

Figure 8 second statement .source author 2022

• **the third statement: Do you suffer from constant moisture in the walls of old cupboards?** The frequency distribution of the answers of the study sample members is clear from Figure 9 that the answer for the majority of the study members is (strongly agree), as their number reached (12) individuals and constituted (63.2%), They followed by those who answered (agree) with (4) individuals at a rate of (21.1%), while the number of those who answered (neutral, disagree and strongly disagree) reached one individual at a rate of (5.3%) for each of them.

Figure 9. the third statement .source author 2022

• **the fourth statement: Do you keep the current design of the cabinets and Niche unchanged?** Frequency distribution of the answers of the study sample members, It is clear from figure 10, that the answer for the majority of the study members is (neutral), as their number reached (12) individuals and constituted (63.2%), followed by those whose answers (Agree) with (5) individuals at a rate of (26.3%), while the number of those who answered (strongly agree) was two individuals at a rate of (10.5%).

Figure 10. the fourth statement source author 2022

• **the fifth statement. Do you reuse cabinets and Niche to suit your own needs?** Frequency distribution of the answers of the study sample members, It is clear from Figure 11, that the answer for the majority of the study members is (I agree), as their number reached (11) individuals and constituted (57.9%), followed by those who answer (strongly agree) (5) individuals at a rate of (26.3%), while the number of those who answered (neutral) was (3) individuals at a rate of (15.8%).

Figure 11. the fifth statement source author 2022

• **the sixth statement. Do you re-repair the damaged cabinets and Niche as soon as any damage occurs to them?** Frequency distribution of the answers of the study sample members, It is clear from Figure 12 that the answer for the majority of the study members is (agree), as their number reached (7) individuals and constitutes (36.8%) While the number of those who answered (strongly agree and neutral) was (6) individuals, at a rate of (31.6%) for each of them.

Figure 12 the sixth statement. source author 2022

5. Discussion

The questionnaires and case studies of houses in the Old City were meant to answer certain questions, Studying several traditional dwellings inhabited by their owners leads to many questions, including the difficulty they may examine in unifying and finding a design link for the furniture and the internal space to maintain the way of life that may lead to modernity in all its aspects and needs, and also the difficulties that face the process of moving furniture to the residential building, as well as the difficulty of finding furniture that suits the design of the traditional dwelling,

especially with the presence of arches and vaults which may not help to arrange a suitable and practical contemporary design. On the other hand, a need to re-design traditional furniture and find spaces for the requirements of modern life, which constitute modern needs that were not present in traditional housing, which is represented by their presence and use in the dwelling, including the kitchen requirements of a place for cooking, the presence of ovens and cooking gases, refrigerators, microwaves, washing machines, and dishwashers, and it also requires the work of sanitary installations for these electrical appliances. Also, finding a suitable space in the bedroom requirements, including beds, wardrobes, and accessories for modern bedrooms, and designing bedrooms that fit the vaulted space, in a way that suits the spirit of the place and use. Among the spaces imposed by contemporary and current modernity are the living rooms and salons, which require a design for seating that fits the arches and domes in the ceilings and walls, and that is suitable for the traditional design of the dwelling, and by using materials close to the spirit of the studied space. The most important points raised in this study and the most important recommendations can be summarized as follows:

- Suffering when buying furniture pieces in the old dwelling.
- suffering from dampness in the walls of old cupboards.
- Adapting and maintaining the current design of the cabinets and Niche without changing their original design.
- Reuse cabinets and Niches to suit the residents' special needs.
- Create a special design of wall cabinets and niches, including their unsuitability for modern use.

6. Recommendations

Studying the history of traditional buildings and their materials and design to preserve and reuse them without losing their identity and to reach advancing results of preservation of the cultural heritage and achieving sustainability. And by Preserving cultural heritage and its preserving identity, We can preserve it without losing its true essence, spirit, and face, and this passes through applying a number of means in order to reach modernity and contemporary in the past spirit and vision, this can be summarized by:

- Developing methods dealing with cultural heritage and providing an opportunity for experimentation and innovation to develop creative capabilities and achieve innovative solutions in interior design and furniture design.
- blending traditional and contemporary furniture design to enrich furniture styles.
- Conducting more research and studies to benefit from the traditional heritage.
- finding a relationship between the original uses of the residential furniture and linking them with the new use as much as possible.
- Attempting to adapt local environment with its raw materials and integrate it into the furniture design in their traditional houses.
- Continuing the periodic maintenance of the residential building to ensure the process of preservation and use.
- Special courses should be introduced in universities and institutes that study the methods of manufacturing furniture suitable for traditional housing so that they are trained to root the originality of traditional buildings in a way that suits modernity and serves the inhabitants of these housing.

In the end, more research is required to take care of the cultural heritage and maintain the condition of the dwelling, making a change that suits their living and does not affect the basic design of the traditional furniture.

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Appendix A. Glossary

Al-Khorang الخورنق: It is the small cabinets called wall cabinets and their measurement varies greatly, including the very small, which is in the lower area of the wall, and from them, it is found in the upper places Table 8.

Almatawa المطوى: Mattress cabinets the word matawa came from folding bedding and other sleeping supplies and the folded is used to place the mattress and is also called the mattress arch and masfat (مسفت) (Hamdan 1996. 631) and there are shelves in the mattress closet and there may be some secret cabinets (Hajj um Safwat. 2019 Personal interview) Table 8.

Namlia نملية: are wooden cabinets that use several uses, including what is placed in the kitchen, where types of dry foods, pickles, and others are stored, as well as used to put household items, and some of them are placed in the hall where the family's belongings of glass and tools are placed, and the ant is the kitchen cabinet in which dishes and others are placed and sometimes called lattice Table 8.

Wejaq وجاق: The stove, they call it on everything related to cooking supplies, where the wajaq was used for cooking and a means of heating, and its measurements varied from one dwelling to another, where it consisted of a rectangle or square where it contained a house of fire and an upper opening that reaches the top of the dwelling, which is called dakhon. The phenomenon of wajaq is widespread in most Palestinian dwellings, as the use of fire in heating is common in most dwellings (Hamdan, 1996, 631). Figure 7.

Alsambuskah السمبوسكه: a triangular wooden shelf for placing the housing supplies (katibih, 2017. 3). Table 8.

Table طاولة: There are different types of tables and depend on their size and use (Hamdan. 1996. 658) Local names for the small table used in hospitality are called Iskamlā or Tarbiza (Ahlam. of Personal Interview 2019) Table 8.

Altablia wood pallet الطبلية : It is a type of short table and has many uses, including for food or study as well as food preparation its session is the dushk, which is a long wooden bench, and some of it is wooden and some of it is upholstered, and when upholstered it is called the sijlon (Hamdan. 658.1996) Table 8.

The bride's box صندوق العروس: The bride at that time was preparing the box as a device to take from her parent's house and go astray with her, which is made of wood and was fed with slices of copper (Sharif, 2004) figure 7.

Altakht (bed) التخت: It is used for sleeping and the bed usually was made of wood.

Cradle المهد: small bed which is placed next to the bed for children (Rogers, 2013.109)

the **sijilon** السجلون (Hamdan. 658.1996) is a long wooden bench with mattresses or mattresses stuffed with wool and the bed is decorated with decorated sheets and embroidered in Table 8.

Chairs and sofas الكراسي والصفوف: varied in shapes, including inlaid and shell sofas, which contain inscriptions and geometric and leafy decorations, as well as carved wooden sofas, and sofas upholstered with dark burgundy velvet. As for the chairs, they were usually made of beech wood (Hamdan. 658.1996) and used to sit on them, whether in the salon or the living rooms. chairs are made of wood and its seat is made of thick hemp threads in the form of weaving upholstery the types vary.

examples of furniture used in the traditional dwelling in the city of Hebron shows Table 8

<p>Al-Khorang</p>	<p>Fixed furniture</p>				
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<p>Table</p>	<p>Mobile Furniture</p>				
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Interview

- Eng. Ahlam Al-Muhtaseb Several interviews (July and August 2019) Information about Palestinian housing over the phone.
- Hajj um Safwat Jabari (July 2019) 75 years old residents of the Old City over the phone
- Nedaa Monotonous Muhtaseb um Omran (July 2019) Age 83 years old residents of the Old City over the phone
- Hajj um Adnan Al-Batsh (July 2019) Age 70 Old City residents over the phone
- Ms. Zulekha Al-Muhtaseb (July 2019) Master of English Language Resident of Shuhada Street and runs a center and has experience in the history of housing in the Old City over the phone.
- Eng. Noha Dundis (2018-2020) is an expert architect and specialist in the residences of the Old City working in the Hebron Reconstruction Committee and was met at the headquarters of the Hebron Reconstruction Committee.
- Mr. Mohammed Al-Housh (2/2015)conducted by Al-Quds TV)